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The Influence of Creativity and Self-Confidence on Craft and Entrepreneurship Learning Outcomes in Bunda Auni Vocational School Students Bekasi

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Abstract

Entrepreneurship has become an important topic in Asian countries. Indonesia's labor index is still low, and below other countries such as Vietnam. The creativity and self-confidence of vocational school students need to be encouraged. The aim of this research is to determine the influence of creativity and self-confidence on the crafts and entrepreneurship of Bunda Auni Vocational School students. The method used is a quantitative method. Data was taken by filling out questionnaires and interviews. The results of the research show that there is an influence of creativity and self-confidence on the crafts and entrepreneurship of Bunda Auni Vocational School students. It is recommended that schools create special programs to improve students' soft skills, so that they are ready to compete to become young and tough entrepreneurs.

Keywords: *creativity, self-confidence, entrepreneurship*

INTRODUCTION

Vocational High School is one of the educational institutions in Indonesia. Vocational Schools are obliged to produce human resources who have professional abilities to apply and develop science, knowledge and technology in accordance with the demands of sustainable national development. Fostering creativity and self-confidence is an important factor in improving craft and entrepreneurship learning outcomes. Active and dynamic students need to be given appropriate challenges, so that their energy can be used well. Hermawati, N. (2021).

Based on the results of observations made by researchers on teachers in the field of crafts and entrepreneurship studies, information was obtained that the cause of a number of students' low learning outcomes was because students were late in submitting assignments and learning test scores did not reach the KKM, apart from that during learning activities students were less active in learning, p. This is characterized by students' inability to generate ideas, answers or questions, students do not dare to express their ideas, are less critical, are not sensitive to environmental situations, lack curiosity, are less open to criticism and are not ready to learn. In fact, to develop knowledge and train skills, this learning begins with training creative expression skills to express ideas and ideas to please other people, and is rationalized technologically so that these skills lead to crafts (Rokhmadi, 2019).

Creativity has quite a big influence on student learning outcomes. Entrepreneurship education is currently directed at creating creative and innovative entrepreneurs. In craft and entrepreneurship learning, students are taught crafts, technology, cultivation and processing (Harianja, M. 2019). In all areas of this material, student creativity is needed to generate ideas, create, be creative and develop. Both in the form of ideas and actual work produced (Harianja, M. 2019). Creativity needs to be fostered, nurtured and developed, especially students' creativity in learning. Student creativity in learning is characterized by the ability to think and solve various problems that occur during learning activities in class. Apart from creativity, other factors are also needed that can have an impact on entrepreneurial results (Suprpto.et all, 2022)

Self-confidence is needed for students to be able to start a business. This activity requires courage and self-confidence (Rahmadani, 2023). Obstacles and challenges to trying are getting tougher and more challenging.

In accordance with the description above, research questions can be asked, namely, does creativity influence craft and entrepreneurship learning outcomes, does self-confidence influence craft and entrepreneurship learning outcomes and do creativity and self-confidence influence craft and entrepreneurship learning outcomes. Meanwhile, the aim of the research is to determine the influence of creativity on craft and entrepreneurship learning outcomes, to find out how self-confidence influences craft and entrepreneurship learning outcomes and to determine the influence of creativity and self-confidence on craft and entrepreneurship learning outcomes at Bunda Auni Bekasi Vocational School.

METHOD

The research method is a scientific way to obtain data with a specific purpose and use. The data obtained through research is empirical or observed data that has valid criteria. Valid shows the degree of accuracy between the data that actually occurs on the object and the data collected by the researcher. According to Sugiyono (2016:2) states that "Research methods are basically a scientific way to obtain data with certain purposes and uses". The research method used in this research is a descriptive method with a quantitative approach. Quantitative research methods, as stated by Sugiyono (2016: 8) "Quantitative research methods are based on the philosophy of positivism, used to research certain populations or samples, collecting data using research instruments, quantitative/statistical data analysis, with the aim of testing hypotheses which has been set.

Data was collected through filling out questionnaires and interviews. The data was processed with the help of SPSS 26. Data on creativity and self-confidence variables were taken based on questionnaires. Meanwhile, variable data on craft and entrepreneurship learning outcomes were taken from report card scores and practical competency tests. Data were tested for assumptions with normality and collinearity. Next, it is processed into the coefficient of determination and multiple regression analysis, T test and F test (Anova). The total sample was 52 students from class XI of the nursing and pharmacy study program.

Gambar 1. Kerangka Berpikir

According to Figure 1 above, there are 3 hypotheses, namely,
Hypothesis 1

H0: there is no influence of creativity on craft and learning outcomes Entrepreneurship

Ha: there is an influence of creativity on craft and learning outcomes Entrepreneurship

Hypothesis 2

H0: there is no influence of self-confidence on craft and learning outcomes
Entrepreneurship

Ha: there is an influence of trust on craft and learning outcomes Entrepreneurship

Hypothesis 3

H0: there is no influence of creativity and self-confidence on learning outcomes
crafts and entrepreneurship

Ha: there is an influence of creativity on craft and learning outcomes Entrepreneurship

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

After carrying out the project-based method, students are given a test to determine the effectiveness of the project-based learning method. or images must be numbered and referred to in the text. The following are the results of SPSS 25 data processing.

Model	Collinearity Statistic	
	Tolerance	VIF
1 (Constant)		
X1	.774	1.244
X2	.674	1.344

VIF is a factor that measures how much the variance of the regression estimator coefficient increases compared to independent variables that are orthogonal if connected linearly. The VIF value will be greater if there is a greater correlation between the independent variables. If the VIF value exceeds 10 then this shows that collinearity is a problem that definitely occurs between independent variables.

Tests of Normality

	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk		
	Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
Hasil_Belajar(Y)	.154	52	.016	.937	52	.018
Kreativitas (X1)	.148	52	.026	.947	52	.021
Kepercayaan (X2)	.101	52	.200*	.967	52	.156

*. This is a lower bound of the true significance.

a. Lilliefors Significance Correction

In the data normality test table above, the Sig value can be seen. the learning outcomes are $0.16 > 0.05$, the creativity value is $0.26 > 0.005$ and the self-confidence value is $0.200 > 0.05$, which means the data has a normal distribution.

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Coefficients Beta		
1	(Constant)	110.690	11.637		9.512	.000
	Kreativitas (X1)	-.104	.116	-.122	-.903	.371
	Kepercayaan (X2)	-.219	.077	-.383	-2.842	.007

a. Dependent Variable: Hasil_Belajar(Y)

In the coefficient table above, the Sig value can be seen. creativity is $0.371 > 0.05$, meaning that the creativity variable influences craft and entrepreneurship learning outcomes. Meanwhile, the self-confidence variable has no effect on craft and entrepreneurship learning outcomes, the Sig. $0.007 < 0.05$

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	683.305	2	341.652	4.099	.023 ^b
	Residual	4083.772	49	83.342		
	Total	4767.077	51			

a. Dependent Variable: Hasil_Belajar(Y)

b. Predictors: (Constant), Kepercayaan (X2), Kreativitas (X1)

In the Anova table, the Sig value. $0.023 < 0.05$ means that there is an influence of variable X1 (creativity) and variable X2 on craft and entrepreneurship learning outcomes. Variables

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted Square	RStd. Error of the Estimate
1	.379 ^a	.343	.108	9.12920

a. Predictors: (Constant), Kepercayaan (X2), Kreativitas (X1)

In the R Square table, it is 0.143, which means that there is an influence of 34.3%, X1 and X2 on Y. This value is intended for the influence of X1 and

DISCUSSION

The results of this research are in accordance with research results (Dewi, et al, 2010) which state that creativity has a strong impact on entrepreneurial learning outcomes, while entrepreneurship requires creativity. This creative nature will make students get more grades because they can complete difficult tasks by ignoring the results they get (Fatah, M. A., & Zumrotun, E. 2023). So that students who have interest, self-confidence and creativity in learning have satisfactory learning results (Rahmadani, 2023). In this sense, self-confidence can arise from the ability to do or do something. So that a new sense of self-confidence emerges after someone does something skillfully and does it in a way that satisfies their heart (Kardiana, T. C., & Melati, 2019). Based on the understanding above, a person will never be a truly confident person, because that feeling of self-confidence appears only in relation to certain skills that he or she has.

The creativity that exists in individuals is used to face various problems that exist when interacting with their environment and look for various alternative solutions so that strong self-adjustment can be achieved (Listiani, N. 2014). Learning outcomes can be interpreted as the level of success of students in studying subject matter at school which is expressed in the scores obtained from test results regarding a number of certain subject matter (Hermanto.et all, 2022)

Self-confidence is a scientific concept that directs human attitudes or behavior to be confident in their own ability to act or act (Thohir.2026). Without self-confidence, humans will not be able to develop themselves and their potential to become better, because high self-confidence is an aspect that greatly influences a person's creative thinking process. Self-confidence is important, because it can make a good contribution to students developing their creative thinking processes (Yohana, 2021).

CONCLUSION

Based on the discussion above, the variables of creativity and self-confidence influence entrepreneurship and craft learning outcomes. These results have the impact that students must improve their soft skills. Vocational school students who are expected to work are encouraged to create job opportunities.

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